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Signs of the Subject and Subjective Side of the Crime of Preparing, Storing, Distributing or Displaying Materials That Threaten Public Safety And Public Order

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Abstract. *In this scientific article, the author cites the concept of "guilt" and its features, which are considered a necessary sign of the subjective side of the crime in the theory of criminal law and law enforcement practice.*

Keywords: *social danger, subjective of crime, criminal law, guilt, guilt, behavior, conscious-voluntary.*

Introduction

In fact, the illumination of the concept of guilt serves: firstly, to reveal the essence of guilt as a psychological phenomenon arising from the commission of a socially dangerous act; secondly, to determine the content of guilt and what its essence is aimed at; thirdly, to determine what the guilt attitude is aimed at (whether the act, its consequences or the crime in general), fourthly, to correctly assess whether the act was committed in a conscious or unconscious mental state or in the interaction of both, fifth In criminal law theory, guilt is usually defined as a person's mental attitude towards the act they are committing and its consequences in the form of intent or negligence¹. As it was said two centuries ago, "The doctrine of guilt, the high and low level of its accurate and complete development, acts as a kind of barometer of criminal law. It is the most effective indicator of the level of civilization of criminal law². Indeed, the definition of guilt plays an important role in the qualification of a crime and the imposition of punishment, and guilt is the "core" of criminal responsibility³ It constitutes. The Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan also identifies guilt as one of the main elements of the committed crime. The verdict determines the guilt (or innocence) of the person, legally assesses their action (or

¹ O'zbekiston yuridik ensiklopediyasi. / Mas'ul muharrir: N. Toychiyev. – Toshkent: Adolat, 2011. – B. 14.

² Feldshteyn G.S. Priroda umysla. – M., 1989. – S. 2.

³ O'zbekiston yuridik ensiklopediyasi. / Mas'ul muharrir: N. Toychiyev. – Toshkent: Adolat, 2011. – B. 14.

inaction), and specifies the type and amount of punishment⁴. Overall, there is no unified approach among scientists and specialists to illuminating this concept. Specifically, according to Sh.E. Abdukadirov, guilt is a psychological attitude of a person towards a socially dangerous act⁵.

According to M.Kh. Rustambaev, "guilt is a manifestation of a person's mental attitude towards a socially dangerous act (action or inaction) committed by them and its socially dangerous consequences in the form of intent or negligence"⁶. According to S. Niyozova, guilt in a crime is not only a mental attitude towards the criminal, but also a person's attitude towards a socially dangerous act and its consequences, which consists of a specific crime committed by them.

With this understanding of guilt, the courts are tasked not with evaluating a person's negative intentions, but with determining whether they are present when a socially dangerous act or inaction is committed. Furthermore, resolving the question of whether a person is guilty or not guilty of committing a specific crime ensures that serious attention is paid to the issue in all aspects⁷. It is not possible to fully agree with the stated opinion, as according to the definition, it creates an incorrect impression that the person committing the crime also has a mental attitude towards another person who has committed a crime.

P. Bakunov proposes the following definition of guilt: Guilt is an integral feature of a crime, expressed in the form of intent or negligence, indicating a person's psychological attitude towards the socially dangerous act they are committing and its socially dangerous consequences⁸. In this given definition, it appears that only crimes with material composition are taken into account, while crimes with formal composition seem to be left out of consideration.

According to O. Yusupjanov, guilt is an abstract concept, it is necessary to reflect the subjective processes that occurred in a person's mind during the commission of a crime, as well as the act that violates, in one way or another, the rules of behavior both regulated and not regulated by legal norms.⁹

According to I.A. Grevnova's interpretation, "guilt is a conscious-psychological attitude of a person towards the socially dangerous act they are committing and its resulting consequences, in the form of intent or negligence, expressing their negative or indifferent view towards the interests of the individual, society, or the state"¹⁰.

V.V. Luneev somewhat expands this definition and defines guilt as "the individual's psychological attitude towards the socially dangerous act they are committing, its socially dangerous consequences, and other legally significant circumstances of the commission of the crime"¹¹. A.V. Grebenyuk proposes that

⁴ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy sudi Plenumining 1997-yil 2-maydagi "Sud hukmi to'g'risida"gi 2-sonli qarori. // www.lex.uz

⁵ Абдукодиров Ш.Ё. Айбнинг эҳтиётсизлик шакли ва унинг белгилари: Ўқув кўлланма. – Тошкент: ТДЮИ, 2005. – Б. 29.

⁶ Rustambayev M.H. O'zbekiston Respublikasi jinoyat huquqi kursi. T. 1. Umumiy qism. Jinoyat to'g'risida ta'limot: Darslik. – Toshkent: ILM ZIYO, 2010. – B. 167.

⁷ Niyozova S.S. O'zgaralar mulkini ishtirokchilikda talon-taroj qilganlik uchun jinoyiy javobgarlik muammolari. Yurid. fan. nom. olish uchun yozil. dis... – Toshkent: TDYUI, 2006. – B. 55.

⁸ Bakunov P.B. Ayb jinoyat sub'ektiv tomonining zaruriy belgisi sifatida. – Toshkent: Adolat, 2006. – B. 46.

⁹ Юсупджанов О.А. Мураккаб айбли жиноятларни квалификация қилиш муаммолари. Юрид. фан. номз. илм. дар. олиш учун ёзил. дисс... – Тошкент: ТДЮИ, 2010. – Б. 29.

¹⁰ Гревнова И.А. Вина как принцип уголовного права Российской Федерации: Дисс. ...канд. юрид. наук. – Саратов, 2001. – С. 52.

¹¹ Luneev V.V. Subyektivnoye vmeneniye. – M., 2000. – S. 12.

guilt should be understood as a person's psychological attitude towards the socially dangerous act they have committed and the socially dangerous consequences that have resulted or may result from the commission of this act¹².

V.A. Yakushin puts forward a more complex definition: "guilt is a legal category that expresses the connection of a person's inner world with the unlawful act being committed, in the form of a mental attitude towards it in certain forms, and therefore is one of the foundations for subjective accusation, qualification of the act, determination of the content and limit of criminal liability for this act"¹³.

The most extensive definition can be found in the work of S.A. Ivanov:

"Guilt is a category provided for in criminal law and having a psychological, moral, legal and social nature, expressing an inevitable sign of the subjective side of the crime, considered a necessary condition for criminal prosecution and punishment, reflecting the psychological (consciously voluntary) attitude of the subject to the socially dangerous act committed by him and the consequences caused by this act, as well as having such conditional indicators as form (intention and negligence), content, degree, essence and scope"¹⁴.

From a subjective perspective, the crime is committed intentionally. The perpetrator understands and desires to establish, lead, or agree to participate in religious extremist, separatist, fundamentalist, or other banned organizations. The motive and purpose of the crime have no significance in its qualification.

The human mind is so complex and yet so simple that it feeds on positive or negative thoughts that enter the subconscious and begins to live with these thoughts. That is, if a person regularly hears information related to ignorance, they may unconsciously start to adopt such thinking. Conversely, if they do not hear these materials, consciously check whether they are prohibited or not through inquiry, and distance themselves from such content, this will yield positive results.

This means that recently, citizens have not been fully aware of the existence of criminal liability for possessing prohibited religious content in information telecommunications. During preliminary investigations, it can be observed that phone owners claim they did not distribute such materials to anyone, stating that they were only listening to or reading them for personal use. It is precisely in this case that our national legislation does not establish liability for storing materials of prohibited religious content. Therefore, the initiation of criminal proceedings in these cases is being reversed. On one hand, this could be seen as upholding citizens' rights and religious freedom, but in today's rapidly changing world, people can easily fall under the influence of various ideological currents.

As mentioned above, when negative thoughts enter the human subconscious, it becomes more likely that a person will unconsciously be directed towards such influences. Citizen N., aged 57, transferred several nasheeds to his son's phone. According to the information received, this person's worldview has changed dramatically recently; he has begun practicing the five daily prayers and incorporating religious knowledge into his speech. When questioned about distributing the content to his son, the individual

¹² Гребенюк А.В. Вина в российском уголовном праве. Автореф. ...дисс. канд. юрид. наук. – Ростов-на-Дону, 2004. – С. 4.

¹³ Якушин В.А., Каштанов К.Ф. Вина как основа субъективного вменения. – Средневолжский научный центр, 1997. – С. 6.

¹⁴ Иванов С.А. Понятие вины и ее основные характеристики в уголовном праве: Дисс. ...канд. юрид. наук. – Ростов-на-Дону, 2004. – С. 29–30.

claims that he sent it not for distribution, but to copy onto a flash drive so he could listen to it in his personal vehicle. To establish the elements of a crime here, it must be proven that he distributed the content.

However, this indicates that he did not distribute it according to his instructions. When the nasheed is examined, it is found to contain prohibited content in Arabic. To initiate a case, the crime must involve distribution, but here it shows the intention was to retrieve it for personal use. Considering the increasing frequency of such cases, it can be seen that citizens are unknowingly obtaining prohibited materials from social networks or acquaintances, and unwittingly storing them on their phones or information storage devices such as flash drives.

The perpetrators of this type of crime are finding and using various methods to deliver prohibited materials to people in order to poison their minds. The more people listen to such nasheeds or lectures, the more their subconscious mind unconsciously begins to draw them towards this direction. Their second stage involves studying the categories of people who have listened to or received such lectures, particularly their material shortcomings, and then begin to lure such individuals into their trap.

This represents a step from fanaticism to extremism. They become capable of quickly implanting ideas into people's minds that threaten the peace of the state and society, aimed at overthrowing the government. As we know, "fanaticism" (from Arabic "aqida" meaning "belief," "attaching one thing to another") refers to the blind application or attempt to apply rules and procedures formed on the basis of strict belief in an idea or principle, absolutizing it without considering conditions, circumstances, or situations. It is vividly manifested in attempts to artificially expand the sphere of influence of certain laws and rules.

A person's happiness in both worlds depends on their beliefs. If one examines cases committed knowingly or unknowingly, one can see citizens who are unknowingly spreading the intellectual nourishment of these fanatical ideas.

Some citizens, without having sufficient religious knowledge, listen to lectures and watch videos from various unofficial websites through the internet. In addition to this, he distributed them to those around him. The constant hearing and seeing of these destructive ideas so affected him that they even thought of "migrating."

Later, they begin to tell their acquaintances about it. However, their behavior does not go unnoticed by family members and the mahalla. The discourse with them will remain in the background. Instead of turning away from this path, they become increasingly involved in alien ideas, and as a result, this work leads them to the black seat of the court

Article 2441 of the Criminal Code states that the social danger of this crime lies in the fact that the preparation of religious materials and their uncontrolled circulation undermines social stability in the state, in particular, the production and distribution of state information of religious content and religion, the import and distribution (sale) of religious literature published abroad on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the weakening of control over the exercise of the powers of the central bodies of religious organizations.

Furthermore, the illegal import of materials containing religious content into the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purpose of their preparation, storage, and distribution poses a real threat, such as illegal religious activity (proselytism, i.e., the involvement of believers belonging to one denomination in another or in

other missionary activities). This, in turn, threatens the emergence of new forms of religious extremism, fanaticism, and separatism. In recent years, there has been an increase in such cases in our country.

On the subjective side, the crime provided for in Article 2441 of the Criminal Code is committed with direct intent, the person realizes that they are committing illegal actions provided for in the disposition of this article and wishes to disseminate materials of religious content. In cases of illegal preparation, storage, or importation of materials of religious content into the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the presence of a dissemination purpose is a necessary sign of the subjective side of the analyzed crime.

In order to prevent the misinterpretation of the concept of materials of religious content in liability for the crime of illegal preparation, storage, import or distribution of materials of religious content in Article 2441 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as to provide a clear definition of the content and apply it in a unified form, we consider it necessary to add an additional comment to the section of the Criminal Code on the legal meaning of the concept of "materials of religious content" given in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 14,

Also, in the comments to the Criminal Code, it is indicated that the motive of this crime can be prejudice, causing religious conflicts, creating instability in society, unlawful overthrow of the constitutional order, often negatively affecting the morality of minors, youth, etc., which creates the impression that the subject of this crime is supposedly prohibited religious literature, that is, it can be confused with the materials specified in Articles 246, 2441, 2443 and 156 of the current Criminal Code. Of course, it would be advisable to develop a resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court on the practice of considering such crimes and provide explanations on such issues.

It is advisable to hold such crimes accountable under criminal law only if they are committed with direct intent, that is, if the cybercriminal understands the socially dangerous nature of their act, sees its socially dangerous consequences, and desires their occurrence.

In practice, in some cases, people unknowingly "like" materials on the Internet to express their attitude, but in this case, these people do not realize the consequences of their actions, that is, they are reacting to this material on the Internet by clicking "like," it does not matter what extremist consequences this material can lead to, the most important thing is that the person likes this information based on their will, willingly and with awareness of its consequences.

As can be seen from the results of the conducted social survey, the age of the person who committed the crime of preparing, storing, distributing or displaying materials that threaten public safety and public order was 18-25 years old (45.5%); 25-35 years old - (45.5%); 35-50 years old - (0%); 50-60 years old - (9.1%); Above 60 years old - (0%).

The subject of this crime is a sane natural person who has attained the age of sixteen before committing the crime. However, considering the fact that these crimes were committed using information technologies and communications, through which individuals under 16 years of age were also able to correctly understand their actions, as well as the fact that a minor also has the ability to fully perform their actions in practice, and the negative consequences of the act are very large, it is proposed to set the minimum age for these crimes in our criminal legislation as 14 years.

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